

IMMEDIATE EFFECT OF SURYANAMASKER ON HEART RATE

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Suryanamaskar is a well-devised mixture of yoga asanas and breathing practices. The series of postures in Suryanamaskar reduce visceral fat, bring flexibility to the spine and limbs, and also enable the practitioner to breathe right. **Aim:** The aim of the present study was to observe the immediate effect of Suryanamaskar on heart rate. **Methodology:** The study was performed at Jadavpur University, department of Physical Education. 15 B.P.Ed male students (23.8 ± 1.89 yrs) were participated in this present study. Subjects were performed 8 round 12 steps Suryanamaskar in the early morning. **Result:** A significant ($p < .05$) effect of Suryanamaskar was found in heart rate. The mean resting heart rate of the study group was 50.60 ± 5.25 beats/minutes increased sharply at 114.40 ± 11.73 beats/minutes after the practice of 8 round of Suryanamaskar. Heart rate were decreased immediately after the exercise and reached 53.93 ± 4.28 beats/minutes at the 10th minute of recovery. **Conclusion:** Thus this present study concludes that Suryanamaskar practice produced a moderate load on heart rate might be a convenient method for the development of cardio-respiratory fitness.

Keywords: *Suryanamaskar, Hear rate, exercise*

1. INTRODUCTION

Surya namaskar (SN), or Salutation to the sun, is an important hatha yogic practice which has been handed down from the sages of vedic time. Surya Namsakar is almost a complete sadhana (practice) in itself, containing asana, pranayama and meditational techniques within the main structure of the practice (Saraswati, 1999). It is reported that regular practice of Suryanamaskar helped to maintain musculo-skeletal and cardio-respiratory fitness of the individual.

The modern era, with the development of science and technology provides man more comfort for his basic necessities. But with these comfort man faces lot of problems, which cannot be solved only by the above facilities. Today the world is looking for solutions to solve the problem of unhappiness, restlessness, emotional imbalance, hyper activity, tension, stress etc through yoga. Regular Suryanamaskar practice improves cardiopulmonary efficiency in healthy adolescents and is beneficial exercise for both males and females. Such yogic practices can be advised to those who are interested to improve the moderate levels of cardiovascular fitness (Bhuktar et.all, 2008). On the other hand heart rate is an important

marker of good health status of the individual. The heart circulates oxygen and nutrient-rich blood throughout the body. When it's not working properly, just about everything is affected. Heart rate is central to this process because the function of the heart (called "cardiac output") is directly related to heart rate and stroke volume (the amount of blood pumped out with each beat).

Suryanamaskar is a good cardiovascular workout which may produce moderate work load on heart. Therefore the main objective of the present study was to observe the immediate effect of Suryanamaskar on heart rate.

2. METHODOLOGY:

2.1 Subject: 15 male B.P.Ed students were participated in the present study. Purposive sampling method was used for collection of data. They were healthy residential male participants, between the ages of 20-25 years. The participants with any kind of injury, ill health were excluded from the study. The study was explained to all participants. The informed consent was obtained from all the participants.

2.2 Design of the study: This is a single group pre-post experimental study. Subject were performed Suryanamaskar for 8 rounds in the early morning with light stomach. Suryanamaskar consisted of a series of 12 steps yogic postures. Heart rate was recorded continuously in three exercise sessions i.e., before exercise, during exercise and after exercise.

Figure:1 Suryanamaskar asanas overview

2.3 Equipment Specification: Resting heart rate, exercise heart rate and recovery heart rate were assessed using the holter monitor (ARYTELL –D, 3 CHANNEL).

Fig no-2 Holter monitor

2.4 Administration of test: On arrival in the laboratory, detail procedure of the test was explained. At first subject was instructed to lie down on the mat in supine position. After that all electrodes was placed one by one on the selected sites of the chest of the body for the study subject. Electrodes were placed on RA, LA, V, RL and LL of the subject's body. Then researcher instructed to the subject to take 10 minutes rest in supine lying position. After 10 minutes rest according to the researcher's exercise protocol subjects were perform 8 rounds of sun salutation. Then subjects again take 10 minutes rest in supine lying position to record the recovery heart rate. After 10 minutes rest researcher take off the all electrodes from the subject's body. Then researcher downloads the data with the help of ARYTELL –D, 3 CHANNEL digital holter analyzer and extract the data from the recorder with the help of the software.

Fig-3 Image of electrodes placement on the selected sites of the subject's body

Table no-1 Experimental session for measuring heart rate:

Measurement of HR(1)	Measurement of HR(2)	Measurement of HR(3)	Measurement of HR(4)	Measurement of HR(5)	Measurement of HR(6)
Resting for 10 minutes	Exercise 8 round SN(Left& Right)	Recovery in 1 minutes	Recovery in 2 minutes	Recovery in 3 minutes	Recovery in 4 minutes

Measurement of HR(7)	Measurement of HR(8)	Measurement of HR(9)	Measurement of HR(10)	Measurement of HR(11)	Measurement of HR(12)
Recovery in 5 minutes	Recovery in 6 minutes	Recovery in 7 minutes	Recovery in 8 minutes	Recovery in 9 minutes	Recovery in 10 minutes

HR- Heart Rate, SN-Surya Namaskar

3. RESULT:

The demographic details of all participants are presented in table no.1

Table: 2 demographic detailed of the participants

Total participants	Age(year)	Weight(kg)	Height(cm)	BMI(kg/mt ²)
15	23.8 ±1.89	62.06±4.31	167.9±5.51	21.98±0.95

Resting heart rate of the study group was 50.60±5.2 beats/minutes. After 8 round of Suryanamaskar practice heart rate were increased up to 114.40±11.73 beats/minutes. Recovery heart rate of each minutes were measured and final recovery heart rate was recorded as 53.93 beats/minutes.

Table no-3: Descriptive Statistics among the Study Group

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Resting Heart Rate (RHR)	50.6000	5.24813	15
Exercise Heart Rate(EHR)	114.4000	11.73396	15
Recovery Heart Rate in 1 min (RHR ₁)	68.6000	7.40463	15
Recovery Heart Rate in 2 min (RHR ₂)	63.8000	6.69968	15
Recovery Heart Rate in 3 min (RHR ₃)	61.2667	6.57340	15
Recovery Heart Rate in 4 min (RHR ₄)	59.7333	6.67048	15
Recovery Heart Rate in 5 min (RHR ₅)	58.4000	6.59870	15
Recovery Heart Rate in 6 min (RHR ₆)	57.8667	6.03403	15
Recovery Heart Rate in 7 min (RHR ₇)	56.8667	6.02218	15
Recovery Heart Rate in 8 min (RHR ₈)	55.5333	4.59606	15
Recovery Heart Rate in 9 min (RHR ₉)	54.3333	4.62395	15
Recovery Heart Rate in 10 min(RHR ₁₀)	53.9333	4.28397	15

TABLE NO-4: Repeated Measure of ANOVA among the Study Group

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F-Ratio	CD
Total	54509.44	179			3.080
Between Subject	4617.78	14	329.841		
Within Subject	49891.67	165	302.374		
Treatments	47093.31	11	4281.210	235.605	
Residual or Interaction	2798.36	154	18.171		

Table no-4 reveals that a significant different were observed among the different time periods of the study group i.e. before exercise(resting heart rate), during exercise(exercise heart rate) and after exercise for a periods of 10 minutes(recovery heart rate). In table no. 5 detail descriptive statistics of the study group in each minute mean value of total experimental session (28 minutes) are given below.

Table-5 Descriptive statistics among the study group in each minute mean value of total training session

	Mean	SD	N
Resting Heart Rate (RHR) in 1 minute	57.86	8.07	15
Resting Heart Rate (RHR) in 2 minute	55.3	6.02	15
Resting Heart Rate (RHR) in 3 minute	53.6	6.12	15
Resting Heart Rate (RHR) in 4 minute	55.5	7.16	15
Resting Heart Rate (RHR) in 5 minute	54	6	15
Resting Heart Rate (RHR) in 6 minute	52	6.1	15
Resting Heart Rate (RHR) in 7 minute	53	5.9	15
Resting Heart Rate (RHR) in 8 minute	53	6.2	15
Resting Heart Rate (RHR) in 9 minute	54	6.9	15
Resting Heart Rate (RHR) in 10 minute	53.4	6.73	15
Exercise Heart Rate(EHR) in 1 minute	74.46	6.35	15
Exercise Heart Rate(EHR) in 2 minute	90.5	12.6	15
Exercise Heart Rate(EHR) in 3 minute	101.9	12.38	15
Exercise Heart Rate(EHR) in 4 minute	106.5	14.12	15
Exercise Heart Rate(EHR) in 5 minute	107	10.7	15
Exercise Heart Rate(EHR) in 6 minute	110	12	15
Exercise Heart Rate(EHR) in 7 minute	110	8.39	15
Exercise Heart Rate(EHR) in 8 minute	108	10.2	15
Recovery Heart Rate in 1 minutes	67.46	6.68	15
Recovery Heart Rate in 2minute	60.2	7	15
Recovery Heart Rate in 3 minute	59	6.1	15
Recovery Heart Rate in 4 minute	58.6	6.17	15
Recovery Heart Rate in 5 minute	60	5.5	15
Recovery Heart Rate in 6 minute	59	6.9	15
Recovery Heart Rate in 7 minute	57	6.4	15
Recovery Heart Rate in 8 minute	58	6.9	15
Recovery Heart Rate in 9 minute	59	7.2	15
Recovery Heart Rate in 10 minute	58	6.7	15

Fig no-4 Graphical representation of mean values of the study group

4. DISCUSSION:

The main emphasis of this study was to observe the immediate effect of suryanamaskar on Heart rate. To fulfil the purpose of the study data were collected and presented in tabular and graphical form. Suryanamaskar is a moderate type of yogic exercise helps to provide a better overall musculo-skeletal and cardiovascular fitness. 15 subjects were participated in the present study, were from the B.P.Ed course of the Department of Physical Education, Jadavpur University. A significant difference of heart rate were observed among there exercise session i.e. before exercise, during exercise and after exercise. In the present study suryanamaskar was used as an exercise intervention to observe the heart rate response of the individual. The mean resting heart rate of the study group was recorded as 50.60 ± 5.25 beats/minutes, heart rate increased sharply and reached at 114.40 ± 11.73 beats/minutes after the practice of 8 rounds of suryanammaskar. Heart rate were decreased immediately after the exercise and reached 53.93 ± 4.28 beats/minutes at the 10th minute of recovery.

On the basis of the present experimental study it can be interpreted that suryanamaskar is a moderate physical activity can be recommended for the maintenance of general cardiovascular health fitness status of the individual. In a study Sinha et.al (2004) reported that during the practice of suryanamaskar the highest heart rate was reached at 101 ± 13.5 beats/minutes. Present researcher also found a similar kind of maximum heart rate (114.40 ± 11.73 beats/minutes) which was reached at the end of 8 rounds (16 times) of continuous suryanamaskar practice. In a study Mody, (2011) also reported that a mean heart rate was reached 90 beats per minute after completion of 4 rounds of suryanamaskar.

A sharp increased of heart rate can be attributed to sympathetic arousal against a moderate work load. Recovery heart rate response was also within the normal physiological function of the individual may attributed to efficient parasympathetic response. Characteristically Suryanamaskar (Sinha et.al.2004), a special set of yogic asanas having both static stretching and dynamic muscular exercise components involving majority of joints, muscles and possibly different internal organ systems of the body, is an all round yogic practices, may be an use full tool to trained cardio- respiratory health.

5. CONCLUSION

Finally we may conclude that, this scientific study may establish the significance of Suryanamaskar as moderate exercise intervention for cardio-respiratory health benefits of the individual. Further we may conclude that 8 rounds of Suryanamaskar could be consider to produce moderate stress on heart thus may prescribed for the individual.

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